

CHEMISTRY

THE STUDY OF THE ALKYLATION REACTIONS OF PHENOL CYCLOHEXENECARBONYL TURPENTINE WITH METHYL ETHER

Naghiyeva M.,

Y.H. Mamedaliyev's Institute of Petrochemical Processes
of the Ministry of Science and Education

Naghiyeva S.,

Gadirova A.

Master's degree student, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University

Abstract

The cycloalkylation reactions of phenol cyclohexenecarbonyl turpentine with methyl ether have been investigated in the presence of zeolite Y catalysts impregnated with KU-23 and ortho-phosphate. Factors influencing the yield and selectivity of the targeted product (temperature, reaction duration, molar ratios of reactants, catalyst quantity) were examined, and optimal conditions for the cycloalkylation reaction were determined. It has been established that under the identified optimal conditions for the cycloalkylation reaction of phenol cyclohexenecarbonyl turpentine with methyl ether: temperature at 115-120°C, reaction duration of 4.5 hours, initial component ratio of phenol to ether at 1:1 mol/mol, catalyst quantity at 7-10% (based on phenol), the yield of 4(4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexanecarbonyl methyl ether ranged from 68.4% to 74.3% (based on phenol), with a selectivity of 89.5% to 94.6% (based on the targeted product).

The influence of our proposed catalysts on the direction of the reaction, the yield and selectivity of the target product was studied and compared with known catalysts used in the alkylation process.

Keywords: alkylation, cyclohexenecarbonyl turpentine, zeolite Y, alkylphenols.

Introduction

The chemistry of phenol compounds is one of the rapidly advancing fields of modern science. There is a growing interest in alkylphenols and their derivatives. The presence of alkylphenol functional groups enables them to undergo oligomerization, polymerization, copolymerization, and condensation reactions, thus offering the possibility of obtaining valuable products from a technical standpoint.

Alkylphenols are considered one of the most important classes of antioxidants. Although amine-based antioxidants are more widely used in industry compared to alkylphenols, the role of phenol-based antioxidants is indispensable in the production process of clear and colorless rubbers.

Various "acid" catalysts are used for the alkylation process of phenol. Lewis acids such as AlCl₃, FeCl₃, BF₃, ZnCl₂, and others; Brønsted acids such as H₃PO₄, H₂SO₄, HF, and various Brønsted acids; and catalysts containing Al₂O₃/SiO₂ are widely used for alkylation reactions [1-5].

• Formulation of the Problem

The investigation of the kinetic regularities of the catalytic cycloalkylation reactions of phenol with methyl ether of cyclohexenecarbonyl turpentine containing a polyaromatic group and the determination of optimal conditions for each reaction have been set as the primary objectives.

• Solution Methods (Experimental Section)

For the alkylation process of phenol, phenol itself, methyl ether of cyclohexenecarbonyl turpentine, and zeolite Y impregnated with KU-23 and ortho-phosphate have been used as reactants.

Before being used for the cycloalkylation process, the phenol taken was purified by distillation. After purification, phenol possessed the following physical-

chemical properties: boiling point $T_q = 182^\circ\text{C}$; melting point $T_{\text{mel}} = 43^\circ\text{C}$; density $\eta_D^{45} = 1.5403\text{g/cm}^3$; refractive index $\rho_4^{25} = 1.0710$; molecular weight = 94.

The methyl ether of cyclohexenecarbonyl turpentine was obtained through a Diels-Alder reaction with the methyl ether of divinyl acrylate and possesses the following physical-chemical properties: boiling range $T_q = 182-183^\circ\text{C}$; density $\eta_D^{20} = 1.4626$; refractive index $\rho_4^{20} = 1.0130$; molecular weight = 140.

KU-23 is characterized by high to medium pore size distribution and has the following composition:

The cation exchange resin KU-23 (modification 10/60 according to GOST 20298) has a pore radius of 250-600Å, ensuring high diffusion rates of reagents (phenol and ether), which in turn allows for the rapid conversion of initial reactants into targeted products. It is thermally stable up to 170°C.

The zeolite-Y catalyst impregnated with ortho-phosphate is prepared by the following method: alumogel and DA-250 industrial cracking catalyst (from "Grace Davison" company) (Zeolite-Y, SiO₂:Al₂O₃ = 4.8, ion exchange degree 97%) are thoroughly mixed. The resulting mass is passed through a sieve with a diameter of 1.6 mm, granulated, and calcined. Then, the catalyst is impregnated with a 10% ortho-phosphate solution (based on P₂O₅), dried at 100°C, and gradually

heated to 200-600°C without interruption for calcination. Subsequently, the obtained catalyst is cooled and used in cycloalkylation reactions.

The chromatographic analysis of the methyl and ethyl ethers of cyclohexanecarbonyl turpentine used in the research was carried out using a Fractovap Model 2150 "Karbon Erba" (Italy) chromatograph equipped with a column with a length of 50 cm and an internal diameter of 0.2 mm, packed with silicone OV-101 stationary phase. The analysis was conducted under the following conditions: helium gas carrier, inlet pressure of 2.4-2.5 kg/cm², separation ratio of 1:150, and a sample volume of 0.3 ml. The initial temperature was set at 30°C, and after 10 minutes, the system was heated at a rate of 2°C per minute.

The molecular weight was determined using a MX-1303 mass spectrometer at a temperature of 200°C, with an ionization voltage of 70 eV and an emission current of 1 mA. The mass spectrum was also obtained using a gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) instrument branded by Hewlett Packard.

The IR spectra of the obtained compounds were recorded using "Spektrum BX" from Perkin-Elmer and "ALPHA IQ Furye" (AFR) spectrometers produced by BRUKER.

The NMR spectra of the obtained compounds were recorded using a 300 MHz NMR spectrometer manufactured by BRUKER (AFR). The ¹H NMR spectra were obtained using a "Bruker WP-400" instrument (¹H 400 MHz, with internal standard - tetramethylsilane).

The elemental compositions of the synthesized compounds were determined using the apparatus available in Laboratory 12 of our institute, manufactured by "Leco Europe B.V." (VOUERSWEG 118-6161 AG GELEEN- NEDERLAND; Postbus 1174-6160 BO GELLEN).

The interaction between phenol and cyclohexanecarbonyl turpentine follows the scheme below:

The optimal conditions for the reaction were studied with the aim of achieving efficient yield and selectivity of the targeted product. Therefore, the influence of various parameters such as reaction temperature, duration, initial component molar ratios, and catalyst quantity on the yield and composition of the reaction products were investigated.

The reaction temperatures ranged from 80 to 140°C, with experimental durations varying from 2 to

6 hours. The catalyst quantity ranged from 5 to 15% (based on phenol), and the molar ratios of phenol to ether ranged from 1:0.5 to 1:2.

The results of the cycloalkylation reaction of phenol with the methyl ether of cyclohexanecarbonyl turpentine in the presence of the KU-23 catalyst are presented in Figure 1.

As seen in Figure 1(a), increasing the reaction temperature from 80 to 120°C leads to an increase in the yield of the targeted product. At 120°C, the highest yield of the targeted product is observed at 68.4% (based on phenol), with a selectivity of 89.5% (based on the targeted product). Further increasing the reaction temperature to 140°C results in a decrease in yield to 64.8% and selectivity to 80.0%. This can be explained by the formation of other undesired by-products alongside the desired targeted product.

As shown in Figure 1(b), increasing the reaction duration from 2 to 4.5 hours leads to an increase in the yield of the targeted product from 37.5 to 68.4%, while selectivity decreases slightly. Further extension of the reaction duration results in a decrease in yield, which can be attributed to the increase in the amount of by-products due to prolonged contact between the reactants and the catalyst.

Increasing the concentration of the ether in the reactant mixture (Figure 1 (c)) leads to a decrease in the yield of the desired product by ~2-3%, which can be explained by the was formed of other isomers in alkylation.

In mutual interaction reactions between methyl ether of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon acid and , one of the main factors affecting the yield and composition of the desired product is the quantity of the catalyst. As shown in Figure 1 (d), achieving the optimal yield of 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl) cyclohexanecarbon turpentine with methyl ether occurs at a catalyst quantity of 10%, resulting in a yield of 68.4% and selectivity of 89.5%.

As a result, it has been determined that the optimal conditions for carrying out the cycloalkylation reaction with the participation of methyl ether of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon acid and using the catalyst KU-23 are as follows: temperature 120°C, reaction duration 4.5 hours, initial component ratios - 1:1 mol/mol for phenol to ether, catalyst quantity - 10% (based on phenol). Under these conditions, the yield of 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl) cyclohexanecarbon turpentine with methyl ether is 68.4% (based on phenol), and the selectivity is 89.5% (based on the desired product).

The preparation of the phosphorus-containing Zeolite-Y catalyst used for cyclic alkylation reactions with cyclic ethers of phenol has been shown above.

Figure 1. Results of the cycloalkylation reactions of phenol with the methyl ether of cyclohexanecarbonyl turpentine in the presence of the KY-23 catalyst

Cycloalkylation reactions of methyl ether of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon acid with under the participation of the ortho-phosphate-treated Zeolite-Y catalyst, unlike those with the KU-23 catalyst, proceed under milder conditions.

Various factors (such as temperature, time, initial component ratios, catalyst quantity) were investigated for their influence on the progress of the reaction to achieve high yield and selectivity of the desired product - 4-hydroxyphenylcyclohexanecarbon acid methyl ether.

Cycloalkylation reactions of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon turpentine with methyl ether under the participation of phosphorus-containing Zeolite-Y catalyst have been investigated at temperatures ranging from 80 to 130°C, reaction durations ranging from 2 to 6 hours, and phenol to ether molar ratios varying from 1:0.5 to 1:2, with catalyst quantities ranging from 5 to 15%.

The results of cyclic alkylation reactions are given in figure 2.

Figure 2. Results of cyclic alkylation reactions of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon turpentine with its methyl ether under the participation of phosphorus-containing Zeolite-Y catalyst

From Figure 2, it is evident that at lower temperatures (80°C), the yield of the desired product is 58.7% (based on phenol), with a selectivity of 82.6% towards the desired product. The lower selectivity is attributed to the formation of alkylphenyl ethers at lower temperatures. With increasing temperature, migration of the alkyl group in the alkylphenyl ether occurs in the ortho position (Claisen rearrangement), leading to the formation of ortho-substituted phenol in the final product.

From the graph, it is evident that at a reaction temperature of 115°C, the yield of the desired product is 74.3% (based on phenol), with a selectivity of 94.6% towards the desired product. Increasing the reaction temperature up to 130°C does not lead to such favorable results. In these conditions, the yield of the desired product decreases to 68.5%, and the selectivity decreases to 87.0%.

Based on the indicators in Figure 2, it can be concluded that a reaction duration of 4.5 hours is more suitable for the interaction of the initial components with the catalyst, as this allows for achieving a more favorable yield and selectivity of the desired product. With

From Figure 2, it is evident that taking a catalyst quantity of 5% for the cycloalkylation reaction does not lead to an economically viable yield of the desired product; under these conditions, the yield is 62.2%, with a selectivity of 95.7%.

The high selectivity is explained by the abundance of initial components that do not participate in the reaction. With subsequent increases in the catalyst quantity, an increase in the yield of the desired product is observed. When the catalyst quantity is 7%, the yield is 74.3%; at 10%, the yield is 76.5%; and at 15%, it is 81.8%. It is evident from the graph that as the catalyst contact surface area increases, the amount of by-products in the final products also increases, resulting in a decrease in selectivity: from 95.7% to 81.8%. Analysis of the results shows that for achieving both a high yield

reaction durations of 2 and 6 hours, it is not possible to obtain a high yield and selectivity of the desired product. Under these conditions, the yields of the desired ether are correspondingly 50.2% and 68.7%, with selectivities of 96.4% and 81.5%.

One of the factors influencing the direction of the reaction for obtaining the methyl ether of 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl) cyclohexanecarboxylic acid is the molar ratios of the initial components taken for the reaction. From Figure 2, it is evident that taking the phenol to ether molar ratio as 1:1 is more advisable because under these conditions, the yield of the desired product is higher at 74.3%, with a selectivity of 94.6%.

Increasing the concentration of phenol in the initial mixture can lead to an increase in the yield of the desired product and the selectivity of the reaction. However, these conditions—achieving only a marginal increase in yield and selectivity by doubling the amount of phenol—are not economically viable.

By increasing the ether in the mixture of primary raw materials by 2-3 times, it can be said that the reaction goes in the direction of the increase of side products, and as a result, 2-mono-, 2,4-di-, 2,6-di- 2,4,6-tri substituted cycloalkylphenols in the alkylate amount increases:

of the desired product (74.3%) and high selectivity (94.6%), it is more advisable to take a catalyst quantity of 7% based on the initial amount of phenol.

Thus, optimal conditions have been identified for the cycloalkylation reaction of phenol's cyclohexanecarboxylic acid methyl ether under the participation of ortho-phosphate-treated Zeolite-Y catalyst: temperature 115°C, reaction duration 4.5 hours, phenol to ether molar ratio 1:1 mol/mol, and catalyst quantity 7% based on the initial amount of phenol. Under these conditions, the yield of 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexanecarboxylic acid methyl ether based on phenol is 74.3%, with a selectivity of 94.6% towards the desired product.

The physical-chemical properties of the synthesized 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexanecarboxylic acid methyl ether are provided in Table 1.

Table 1.

Physical-chemical properties of 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexanecarbon acid methyl ether

Structural formula	$T_{\text{boil.}}$ 5 mm Hg, °C	η_D^{20}	ρ_4^{40}	Molecular mass	Calculated, %	
					Found, %	
					C	H
	166-168	1.4920	1.0040	234	71.7 71.3	7.6 7.4

Table 2 provides the yields, selectivities, and compositions of cycloalkylation reactions of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon turpentine with methyl ether under the participation of known and proposed catalysts at optimal conditions.

Table 2

Comparative indicators of cycloalkylation reactions of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon turpentine with methyl ether under the participation of various catalysts.

Conditions \ Catalyst	NaHSO ₄ (known)	KU-2 (known)	KU-23	Zeolit-Y +H ₃ PO ₄
Temperature, °C	125	130	120	115
Time, hour	5.5	6	4.5	4.5
Phenol:ether, mol/mol	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
amount of catalyst, %	12	12	10	7
Composition of cycloalkylation reactions, % mass				
Cycloalkylphenyl ether	2.3	2.0	1.3	—
2- Monocycloalkylphenol	3.3	3.8	2.8	2.3
4- Cycloalkylphenol	83.5	82.7	89.2	93.4
2,4-; 2,6-di-substituted phenol	3.6	3.0	1.7	1.5
2,4,6-tri-substituted phenol	5.2	5.7	3.6	3.1
Residue	2.1	2.8	1.4	0.7
Yield, %	63.0	65.7	68.4	74.3
Selectivity, %	90.2	86.3	89.5	94.6

From the table, it can be seen that compared to known catalysts, the catalysts we proposed (KU-23, or ortho-phosphate-treated Zeolite-Y) enable the alkylations to be carried out under milder conditions (115-120°C, 4.5 hours, phenol:ether 1:1 mol/mol, catalyst quantity 7-10%), resulting in achieving high yields of the desired product (68.4-74.3%).

4. Conclusion

Cycloalkylation reactions of phenol's cyclohexanecarbon acid with the methyl ether under the participation of the KU-23 and ortho-phosphate-treated Zeolite-Y catalysts have been conducted, and optimal conditions have been determined.

The influence of the catalysts we proposed on the direction of the reaction and the yield and selectivity of the desired products has been investigated and compared with known catalysts used for the alkylation process.

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